

Rac-4d

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-85-RAC-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	31	Acq. Method Set:	20% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	XT 2 85 RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	30.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	8/5/2021 7:04:44 PM CST		
Date Processed:	8/6/2021 10:23:50 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	9.207	9368825	52.59	685041
2	10.095	8444421	47.41	548260

Asy-4d

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-87'-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	33	Acq. Method Set:	20% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	XT 2 87
Injection Volume:	2.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	14.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	8/6/2021 10:39:12 AM CST		
Date Processed:	8/6/2021 10:55:30 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	9.206	12316620	99.03	915624
2	10.073	120446	0.97	8473